

HISTORY OF DEVELOPMENT OF REPRESENTATIVES OF TWO GENERA – BULIMINA AND BOLIVINA IN SARMATIAN BASIN OF PARATETHYS

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Abstract

The analysis of an actual material demonstrated that on the territory of Paratethys in the Sarmatian basin the genus *Bolivina*, similarly to *Bulimina* is neither widespread nor characterized by a large number of species. The great majority of the species is phylogenetically connected with Middle Miocene *Bolivina*; their numerous populations existed in all regions of Paratethys. In the Miocene basins there were conditions close to the seas of normal salinity, more or less favorable for *Bolivina* and promoting their reproduction. After deterioration of ecological conditions during the Sarmatian time caused by interruption of link with the normal salinity sea, *Bolivina* occurred in conditions unfavorable for their existence. Their majority, which could not adjust to the existing conditions, died out and as for the preserved forms they gradually declined.

The facts show that *Bulimina* and *Bolivina* are observed within the rocks deposited in relatively deep areas, which are formed in the zones of maximum settling and mainly represented by clays. It is known that ecological conditions at a depth are more stable as compared to the coastal line or shallow areas and aren't subjected to abrupt alteration.

Introduction

Among whole Sarmatian foraminifera so-called Mediterranean type of stenohaline group of foraminifera is sharply distinguished. The following genera belong to this group: *Bulimina*, *Bolivina*, *Discorbis*, *Cassidulina*, *Hauerina*, *Anomalina*, *Cibicides*, etc. Whereas the bigger part of properly Sarmatian endemic euryhaline species are characterized by intensive interspecific changeability, high rate of origin of species, tendency of increase of specimens in time and by well developed ornamentation of tests. The stenohaline forms are distinguished by very small sizes, tendency to simplification of structure of aperture and test. Besides, they are characterized by narrow areas of distribution. Here we will consider only two genera (*Bulimina*, *Bolivina*) about which in literature are somehow more data.

Discussion

In huge Sarmatian basin of Paratethys the representatives of genus *Bulimina* can be seen only in some regions (Tab.I), where they are represented by small number of species. The history of development of *Bulimina* in Sarmatian time is a good example of influence of environment on fauna, when the conditions of life evoked not the flourishing and expansion of forms, but their depression and regeneration.

On the territory of Western Georgia in Middle Sarmatian deposits of gorges of rivers Ochkhamuri and Chanistskali the single species of genus *Bulimina* – *B.aff.elongata* d'Orb. (Pl.I, fig.8a,b, 9a,b) was observed. Usually the tests of this species are characterized by small sizes (length – 0.70 mm; width – 0.20 mm), but the Middle Sarmatian forms are of very small sizes (length – 0.30 mm; width – 0.15 mm), we can say that they are “pygmy”. The outlines of tests are nearly cylindrical (the typical form is nearly cone), the number of chambers is no more than 7- 9, the test is short, the form of aperture is like chink. By morphological sign they are like Late Konkian and Kosovian specimens. By opinion of researchers studying recent foraminifera (Saidova, 1961; Shchedrina, 1950; Phleger, 1960; Boltovskoy, 1965) such structure of test is unusual and

connected with deterioration of life conditions. There are many reasons of oppression of foraminifera: decrease of salinity, disturbance of nutrition regime, values of oxygen, calcium carbonate and pH, the composition of protoplasm, etc. By opinion of Turkish specialists (Meric et al., 2004) for recent species of genus *Bulimina* (among them the typical *B.elongata* is implied) in Aegean Sea with normal salinity the optimal conditions are near beach, from 60 m up to 5000 m, where the salinity is 35-40‰. In past time the favorable conditions for *Bulimina* was in Eocene and Badenian basins with normal salinity. For deposits of this age *Bulimina* is often used as zonal form.

The forms like *Bulimina aff.elongata* from Sarmatian deposits of Western Georgia were seen also in Middle Sarmatian deposits of Viselkovsky region (Pre-Caucasus). In collection of Bogdanowicz and Gnedina (Pl.I, fig.5a,b, 6,7) these forms are of small sizes, transparent, with delicate glassy walls and with 7-9 chambers. By opinion of these authors they descended from Middle Miocene ancestors in condition of fresh-water Sarmatian basin. From other locality similar forms, such as *Neobulimina sp.n.* were described by Bogdanowicz (1965). He considered them as descendants of *Neobulimina elongata* from Konkian stage.

It is known, that *Bulimina* has three rows of chambers coiled in spiral, but for *Neobulimina* three rows of chambers occurred on initial stage are changed into two rows. The Sarmatian forms are very small and such change of chambers is not noticed. So by our opinion it is better to preserve name *Bulimina aff.elongata* and consider it as the descendants of *Bulimina elongata* from Konkian. The last is widely distributed in Konkian deposits of Eastern Paratethys (Bogdanowicz, 1965; Djanelidze, 1970; Krasheninnikov et al., 2003) and in Badenian of Western Paratethys (Popescu, 1979). Popescu's opinion about taxonomic significance of genera *Bulimina* and *Caucasina* deserve the attention. As we noted above, the typical *Bulimina* has three rows of chambers arranged in spiral. Such forms are widely distributed in deposits of different age and in recent seas. In Miocene basins and especially in Sarmatian, structure of their test is somewhat simplified due to less number of chambers. In whole the test received cylindrical outline. Small forms of *Bulimina*, which test has such outline and simple structure were united by Khalilov (1951) in new genus *Caucasina*.

In Popescu's work (1979) where Kosovian (Upper Badenian) foraminifera are described, *Bulimina* and *Caiucasina* with simplified test are united one in genus *Baggatella* Howe, 1939. According to Popescu Howe was the first who noticed the tendency towards simplification of test in this group of foraminifera and united them in one genus *Baggatella*. In this work *Bulimina* and *Caucasina* from Miocene are described as *Baggatella*. Those are the following forms: *Bulimina elongata*, *B.elongata var.subulata*, *B.pineiformis konkensis*, *B.gutsulica*, *Caucasina lalovi* and *C.schischkinskye*.

Bulimina aff.pyrula from Middle Miocene deposits of Black Sea depression was determined by Didkovsky (1962). This species was observed only in 3 sections from described in this work 41 ones. But neither description nor photos of this form were given by Didkovsky.

Near village Migura (Moldova) in Middle Sarmatian deposits *Bulimina elegans* and *B.elongata* are noted by Bobrinskaya and Burindina (1981). Besides, in wells drilled on Central platform of Moldova *B.aff.elongata* and *B.elongata* were determined in composition of Middle Sarmatian complex of foraminifera (Bobrinskaya, Kurenkova, 1986). In Middle Sarmatian deposits of borehole near v. Zelenaya *B. elongata elongata* and *B.aculeata* were also seen.

Among other regions of Western Paratethys the Pre-Carpatian (Western Ukraine) should be noted, where *Bulimina pineiformis* from Sarmatian deposits and its varieties – *B.pineiformis var.subulata morfa dimediata*, *B.pineiformis elegans var.subulata*, *B.pineiformis elegans var.pupoides* were described by Livental (1953). Two last forms are similar and very resemble to *B.aff.elongata* distinguished by us. Besides, by opinion of Livental the forms described from Sarmatian deposits of Pre-Carpatian represented the allied group for *B.elongata* that is in agreement with our opinion. They are of small sizes, have simple structure and nearly cylindrical outline.

In Lower Sarmatian deposits of Romania the following varieties – *Bulimina gibba*, *B.elongata elongata*, *B.elongata vagina* – are noted by Paghida-Trelea (1969). In this complex varieties of *B.elongata* are dominated.

By data of Korecz-Laky (1968, 1973) in Lower Sarmatian deposits of Hungary *Bulimina pupoides* is presented. As it was mentioned above this species by Livental is the relative of polymorphic *Bulimina pineiformis*, which for its part is the relative of *B.elongata*.

In Hungary (basin of Zambek) in three zones of Sarmatian deposits (*Elphidium regium*, *E.hauerinum*, *E.austriaca*) *B.elongata* and *Caucasina schischkinskye* are presented. In work devoted to Oligocene-Miocene of Central Paratethys (Cicha et al., 1998) the last species is described as *Bulimina schischkinskye*. Besides, in the Sarmatian deposits of Hungary *Bulimina elegantissima* was seen, which was presented only in two first zones. The independence of these three species up today is the subject of dispute. According to the data of Gorog (1992) the tests of these species are very small. The length and diameter are nearly equal.

On territory of North-Western Bulgaria, near v. Galatin in Lower Sarmatian deposits dated by mollusk *Bulimina gutschulica* was determined (Stancheva, 1960).

From Lower Sarmatian deposits of Poland *Bulimina micra* was described (Luczkowska, 1971). The name of this form was connected with small size of test.

Without comparison with original material it is difficult to speak about correctness in determination of all above mentioned forms or their taxonomical value, as their pictures (the drawings are always subjective) are inferior. Some discussed species have no description, because some of them are only in lists of fauna. In spite of this it is no doubt that Sarmatian species are descendent of Middle Miocene *Bulimina*, which were widely distributed in basins of Paratethys and represented by many species. But in Sarmatian basins they occurred in unfavorable conditions. In comparable deep sites of sea the poor and depressed populations were originated, which occupied more or less free niches with comparative optimal conditions. In basins of Lower Sarmatian the number of species was enough high (11), but in Middle Sarmatian only 3 forms were preserved. As it can be seen from analysis of fauna, in Sarmatian genus *Bulimina* was represented by related forms, which among other species of this genus were more resistant and able to adapt deterioration of life conditions.

On the territory of Western Georgia in lower part of Middle Sarmatian deposits (outcrop on river Chanistskali) genus *Bolivina* is represented by three species: *Bolivina sarmatica*, *B.nisporenica* and *B.aff.dilatata* (Pl.I), which are very similar to *Bolivina dilatata brevis*, described by Cicha (Cicha, Zapletalova, 1963). In Slovakia this form is characteristic for Badenian, but in Western Ukraine for Middle Sarmatian (Venglinsky, 1975). The forms similar to *Bolivina aff.dilatata* from Konkian (Sartaganian) deposits of Georgia were described by Djanelidze (1970). The species from Middle Sarmatian differed from Konkian forms by comparable short and "thick" test and smaller number of chambers. *B.aff.dilatata* is also alike *Bolivina dilatata*, described by Krashennikov from Konkian deposits of North Caucasus and Crimea. Author compares this species with forms, which are widely distributed in Badenian deposits of Ukraine and have the same name. They differ from one another only by sizes. The forms from Crimea-Caucasian region are smaller and have less number of chambers.

Five new species of genus *Bolivina* from Middle Sarmatian (cryptomactrian) deposits of Moldova (district Nisporen) were described by Didkovsky. Those are: *B.moldavica*, *B.nisporenica*, *B.sarmatica*, *B.sagittula* and *B.sinzovii*. First two species are similar. It must be noted that the megaspherical individual of *B.moldavica* is given on plate, but for *B. nisporenica* the microspherical specimen was chosen by author. So, the small difference between them can be explained by drawing the picture of test of different modifications. The microspherical specimen is always more long and narrow and has more chambers than megaspheric one.

According to our observations mentioned above forms are very similar with *B.aff.dilatata* from Middle Sarmatian deposits of river Chanistskali and also with *B.dilatata* from Middle Miocene (Konkian) deposits of Crimea-Caucasus, which by our opinion are ancestors of Sarmatian forms.

The same can be said about *B.sarmatica* and *B. sagittula* described by Didkovsky. The megaspherical form of *B.sarmatica* is given on plate, and for *B.sagittula* - the picture of microspherical specimen. According to description they are differed by length, width and number of chambers, that is usual phenomenon for megaspherical and microspherical forms.

From Sarmatian deposits of Nakhichevan 4 species of *Bolivina* and 1 subspecies were described by Pronina (1964). Among them *B.pseudoantegressa*, *B.concina* and *B.duzdagica* are from Lower Sarmatian and *B.chalilovi* and *B.chalilovi khyndjabica* from Middle Sarmatian. According to description and plates, *B.pseudoantegressa* and *B.concina* are similar forms. They are distinguished only by sizes of tests (I - length 0.28mm; width - 0.15mm; thickness - 0.10mm; II - length 0.22mm; width - 0.16mm; thickness - 0.11mm) and number of chambers (I - 8; II - 6). The differences are so small, that the possibility of their separation as independent species is doubtful. Besides, it is necessary to take in consideration, that *B.pseudoantegressa* is Konkian-Lower Sarmatian form and *B.concina* - Middle Sarmatian. Probably increasing of sizes of *B.concina* was connected with unfavorable conditions of Middle Sarmatian. All described species Pronina compared with the forms from Eocene and Oligocene and by her opinion the main differences are in outline of tests. It is likely that Pronina did not know the work of Didkovsky (1959) on *Bolivina*. Otherwise she would at first compare the species from Azerbaijan with those from Ukraine, because similarity between them is very great. Comparison of descriptions shows, that definite likeness is between *Bolivina duzdagica* and *B.moldavica*; *B.chalilovi* and *B.sarmatica*. The definite similarity is also between *B.chalilovi var.khyndjabica* and *B.sagittula*. Establishment of new species of foraminifera from Sarmatian deposits of Nakhichevan was connected with practical interest, because if some group of foraminifera is distributed on one and same level it becomes the index fossil. By mean of such group it is easy to date and correlate the deposits. Unfortunately, while determination of the new species researchers were not often taken into consideration the phylogenetic ties

and ecogenesis. Ignoring of these factors is often the reason that in base of new species are put morphological differences between typical and changeable forms connected with environmental changes.

For the first time Livalent (1953) described representatives of genus *Bolivina* (*B.aff.punctata* and *Bolivina sp.*) from Sarmatian deposits of Western Paratethys. In Poland from Lower Sarmatian deposits (Tarnobrzeg-Chmielnik region) the following species were described by Luczkowska (1964): *B.variabilis*, *B.vienensis*, *B.dilatata*, *B.hyalina*, *B.polonica*. In Sarmatian complex of foraminifera they are represented by single specimen and distinguished by small sizes.

The data about *Bolivina* from Miocene deposits of Western Carpathian are presented in work of Cicha and Zapletalova (1963), where more than 40 species and subspecies are described. They are grouped according two signs: by their relationship ties, from one hand, and by area of distribution, from other. Ecological relative forms are divided as follows: 1. very stenohaline species; 2. temperate stenohaline species; 3. comparable eurihaline species.

The species from Sarmatian deposits belong to the third group: *Bolivina sagittula*, *B.pappi*, *B.moravica*, *B.moldavica granensis*, *B.aff.sarmatica*, *B.pseudoplicata*. By Cicha and Zapletalova along with those species depressed and ugly representatives of *Bulimina*, *Cassidulina* and *Virgulina* existed on deep sites of Sarmatian Sea. They explained the variability of *Bolivina* in Sarmatian basins by transgression distributed from East to West. Owing to this fact the differences between Badenian and Sarmatian *Bolivina* were considered as regular phenomenon, that by opinion of authors, complicates the establishment of phylogenetic ties. The Sarmatian *Bolivina* migrated from Eastern were considered as endemic species.

The data about numerous representatives of *Bolivina* from Sarmatian deposits of Carpathian area are given in the work of Venglinsky (1975). By author in Lower Sarmatian deposits Dorobratovian and Lucovian suits are distinguished and in Middle Sarmatian – Almashian suit. For Dorobratovian suit representatives of genus *Bulimina* are zonal forms and due to their dominated position the name of zone is *Cibicides badensis* and *Bolivina sarmatica*. In Almashian suit *Bolivina sarmatica* with *Caucasina* subzone is distinguished. In Dorobratovian suit the following forms are dominated: *B.nisporenica*, *B.sarmatica*, *B.aff.directa*. In Almashian suit *B.dilatata brevis*, *B.sarmatica brevissima* are prevailing. In both suits the specimens of *B.aff.tarchanensis* are rarely represented. Among mentioned above species *B.sarmatica* and *B.nisporenica* are proper Sarmatian forms, which originated from Middle Miocene species and formed as independent units. In lower layers of Lower Sarmatian *B.aff.directa* and *B.aff.tarchanensis* are represented by more number of specimens, than in upper layers, where only single forms occur. In Middle Sarmatian the number of these species increased. As for subspecies *B.dilatata brevis*, *B.sarmatica brevissima*, *B.aff.sarmatica* and partly *B.plicatella mera* in Middle Sarmatian they are represented by great number of specimens.

On the territory of Northern Moldova (v.Drepkautsi) in samples from borehole with typical Lower Sarmatian complex of foraminifera, *B.sarmatica* and *B.aff.subdilatata* were determined (Bobrinskaya, 1986). The samples from same borehole contained also complex of Middle Sarmatian foraminifera: *B.aff.subdilatata*, *B.aff.sagittula*, *Bolivina sp.*

In Moldova on the territory of Central Platform (near v.Ulma) in samples, which were took from borehole together with typical Middle Sarmatian foraminifera - *B.sarmatica*, *B.nisporenica*, *B.punctata*, *B.aff.arta*, *Bolivina sp.* – planktonic foraminifera were seen (Bobrinskaya, Kurenkova, 1986). In this borehole representatives of genus *Bolivina* were seen also in Upper Sarmatian deposits. Those are: *Bolivina subdilatata* and *Bolivina sp.* This is the unique case, when in Upper Sarmatian deposits together with remains of fresh water Characeae the planktonic forms of normal salinity and *Bolivina* are presented.

Among samples collected by Paramonova on territory of Eastern Serbia (river Arau) the Middle Sarmatian complex of foraminifera was determined by Maisuradze. In this complex the following species of *Bolivina* were: *B.sarmatica*, *B.sarmatica brevissima*, *B.aff.directa*, *B.scalprata miocenica*, *B.dilatata brevis*, *B.aff.arta*. The fauna is very small, ugly forms can be seen often. By composition of *Bolivina* and *Hauerina* this complex is similar to association, which was described by Venglinsky from Almashian suit (Carpathian region). At the same time Middle Sarmatian complex of Serbia is similar to synchronous complex of Moldova. In composition of both complexes common species of *Spirolina* are presented.

From Middle Sarmatian deposits of Romania *B.moldavica*, *B.sarmatica* and *B.pseudoplicata* were described by Paghida-Trelea (1969). By data of author the last species is more often presented in deposits of Badenian and Buglovian, than in Sarmatian sediments.

The presence of *B.moldavica* in Middle Sarmatian deposits of Romania was also indicated by Ionesi (1968).

In Lower Sarmatian deposits near v.Girleu *Bolivina sp.*, *B.dilatata*, *B.ex gr. scalprata*, *B.ex gr. pokorny* were determined by Paghida-Trelea (1969) and Simionesku (1967).

By data of Simionesku (1966, 1969, 1977) in the vicinity of Bakeu (gorges of r.Bistritsa and Trebish) in deposits of Middle Sarmatian (cryptomactrian clays) were seen: *B.sagittula*, *B.aff.sarmatica*, *B.nisporenica*, *B.moldavica*, *B.tarchanensis*, *Bolivina* sp. (Tab.2).

As it can be seen from analysis of material in Sarmatian basins of Paratethys species of genus *Bolivina* were not widely distributed. In most cases they are represented by related forms and if not the subjective approach of researchers the number of determined species would be much less. Phylogenetic Sarmatian representatives of genus *Bolivina* are connected with Miocene forms, which numerous populations on whole territory of Paratethys were widely distributed. In the Middle Miocene basins optimal for their existence conditions were those close to sea with normal salinity. In Sarmatian time, when the connection with the open sea was interrupted the ecological conditions in basins sharply changed and foraminifera occurred in unfavorable situation. Many of them were not adapted to new conditions and extinct. Some of preserved forms were depressed but some, more strong began reproduction and occupied the free niches. Some depressed foraminifera, for example *Bolivina*, changed their morphological structure and continued to exist in Sarmatian basins - till Middle Sarmatian (tab.2).

Conclusion

Thus, on the base of analysis of factual material it can be concluded:

1. In Middle Miocene basins of Paratethys species of genera *Bulimina* and *Bolivina* occupied rather big area. In some regions of Pannonian basin (basin of Vienna, Carpathian basin) due to predominant position of these genera their names are used for stratigraphical zones. In Lower Sarmatian basins populations and area of distribution of genera *Bulimina* and *Bolivina* decreased. This process was continued in Middle Sarmatian. *Bolivina* compared with *Bulimina* appeared more resistant, because in spite of depression the endemic species and more often the subspecies were formed.

2. In spite of difficult connection between regions *Bulimina* and *Bolivina* were migrated from Western Paratethys to Eastern Paratethys. As it is known in Western Paratethys Middle Miocene complexes of foraminifera are more rich in representatives of *Bulimina* and *Bolivina*, than synchronous complexes of Eastern Paratethys. Therefore we suppose, that lower boundary of Sarmatian in Pannonian basin is on lower stratigraphical level, than in Dacian basin and much lower in Ponto-Caspian basin. So why the Lower Sarmatian transgression comparably earlier began in Western Paratethys and somewhat late in Eastern, that is confirmed by existence of Mediterranean type of fauna in Rhisioian deposits of Vienna basin (Muskhelishvili, 1980).

3. Probably one and the same species which developed in unstable conditions of different regions of Paratethys, in spite of synchronous age obtained somewhat different morphological signs. the sizes of test and outline of aperture were changed more often. In recent *Bulimina* and *Bolivina* the aperture is bigger and more open, in fossil forms it is relatively narrow and high.

4. The representatives of *Bulimina* and *Bolivina* in Middle Sarmatian is nearly everywhere connected with deposits of deep sea, which sedimentation occurred in zones of maximum setting. In such places the changes of conditions, especially of salinity was not as sharp as in coastal zone. So why in deposits of this zone the marine microfauna is rare or fully absent.

5. The researcher of recent benthic foraminifers Murray (1973) noted, that in Mediterranean Sea *Bulimina*, *Bolivina*, *Cassidulina*, etc. prefer the muddy ground. For their existence the composition of mud and the quality of sand material mixed in it was significant. For them optimal situation is, when ecological conditions of biotopes and the composition of communities for a long time preserved the stable position. In such situation foraminifera are less changeable.

6. By literature data in Sarmatian deposits of Paratethys genus *Bulimina* is represented by 11 species, 3 varieties and 1 subspecies. Genus *Bolivina* is represented by 27 species and 8 subspecies. But in resuming work on Central Paratethys (Cicha et al., 1998) the data about *Bulimina* from Sarmatian deposits are absent. As for *Bolivina*, there are data only about one species (*B.sarmatica*).

So, this fact ensure us that detail and probably critical analysis of each published material is necessary for establishment of the systematical composition of foraminifera fauna and revealing the inaccuracy in determination, as well as for analysis of conditions of sedimentation and ecology of Sarmatian Sea of Paratethys.

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Plate 1.

- 1a,1b,2a,2b – *Bolivina sarmatica* Didkovsky, West.Georgia, river Chanistskali, x100;
- 3a,3b – *Bolivina aff.dilatata* Reuss, West.Georgia, river Chanistskali, x100;
- 4a,4b – *Bolivina nisporonica* Didkovsky, West.Georgia, river Chanistskali, x100;
- 5a,5b,6, 7 – *Bulimina aff.elongata* d’Orbigny, Pre-Caucasus, Viselkovsky region, (collection of Bogdanowicz and Gnedina), x100;
- 8a,8b,9a,9b - *Bulimina aff.elongata* d’Orbigny, West.Georgia, village Ochkhauri, x100.

Table 1. Distribution of species of *Bulimina* in the Sarmatian deposits of Parathetis

F a u n a		Poland	Hungary	Precaucasian	Bulgaria	Moldova	Ukraine	Romania	Precaucasian	Georgia					
№ / №	B u l i m i n a	S ₁	S ₂												
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15
1	<i>Bulimina elongata</i> d’Orbigny		+				+			+	+		+		+
2	<i>B. aff. elongata</i> d’Orbigny						+								
3	<i>Neobulimina elongata</i> Bogdanowicz												+		
4	<i>Neobulimina</i> sp.												+		
5	<i>Bulimina</i> sp.						+				+				
6	<i>B. aff. pyrata</i> d’Orbigny								+						
7	<i>B. elegans</i> (d’Orbigny)						+								
8	<i>B. aculeata</i> d’Orbigny						+								
9	<i>B. pineiformis</i> (Soldani)				+										
10	<i>B. pineiformis</i> var. <i>subulata morfa dimendiata</i> Livalent				+										
11	<i>B. pineiformis</i> var. <i>elegans subulata</i> Livalent				+										
12	<i>B. pineiformis elegans</i> var. <i>pupoides</i> Livalent				+										
13	<i>B. gibba</i> Fornasini														
14	<i>B. elongata vagina</i> Pishvanova										+				
15	<i>B. pupoides</i> d’Orbigny		+								+				
16	<i>B. gutsulica</i> Livalent				+										
17	<i>B. micra</i> Luczkowska	+													
18	<i>B. subulat</i> Cushman and Parker									+					

Table 2. Distribution of species *Bolivina* in the Sarmatian deposits of Parathetis

№ / №	F a u n a	Slovenia		Hungary		Slovakia		Poland		Western Ukraine		Romania		Moldova		Georgia		Azerbaijan	
		S ₁	S ₂	S ₁	S ₁	S ₁	S ₁	S ₂	S ₁	S ₂	S ₁	S ₂	S ₁	S ₂	S ₁	S ₂	S ₁	S ₂	
		2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16			
1	<i>Bolivina sarmatica</i> Didkovski	+						+	+		+	+		+					
2	<i>B. dilatata</i> Reuss					+				+							+		
3	<i>B. dilatata brevissima</i> Cicha et Zapletalova		+					+	+								+		
4	<i>B. aff dilatata</i> Reuss																+		
5	<i>B. nisporonica</i> Didkovski		+					+	+		+		+						
6	<i>B. moldavica</i> Didkovski										+		+						
7	<i>B. sagittula</i> Didkovski				+						+		+						
8	<i>B. sinzovi</i> Didkovski												+						
9	<i>B. pseudoantegressa</i> Pronina																	+	
10	<i>B. concina</i> Pronina																	+	
11	<i>B. duzdagica</i> Pronina																	+	
12	<i>B. chalilovi</i> Pronina																		+
13	<i>B. chalilovi khindjabica</i> Pronina																		+
14	<i>B. pappi</i> Cicha et Zapletalova				+														
15	<i>B. moravica</i> Cicha et Zapletalova				+														
16	<i>B. moldovica granensis</i> Cicha et Zapletalova				+														
17	<i>B. aff sarmatica</i> Didkovski				+						+		+						
18	<i>B. aff directa</i> Cushman		+					+											
19	<i>B. pseudoplicata</i> Her-All et Earl				+					+	+								
20	<i>B. sarmatica brevissima</i> Venglinsky				+					+									
21	<i>B. aff tarchanensis</i> Subbotina et Chutzieva							+	+		+								
22	<i>B. aff arta</i> Macfadyen		+								+								
23	<i>B. plicatella mera</i> Cushman et Ponton																		
24	<i>B. scalprata miocenica</i> Macfadyen		+																
25	<i>B. aff punctata</i> d'Orbigny							+	+										
26	<i>Bolivina</i> sp.							+		+	+								
27	<i>B. variabilis</i> Luczkowska					+													
28	<i>B. vienensis</i> Luczkowska					+													
29	<i>B. hyalina smigelsca</i> Luczkowska					+													
30	<i>B. polonica</i> Bieda					+													
31	<i>B. punctata</i> d'Orbigny			+							+								
32	<i>B. aff subdilatata</i> Pishvanova									+									
33	<i>B. aff sagittula</i> Didkovski										+								
34	<i>B. ex gr. scalprata</i> Schager									+									
35	<i>B. ex gr. pokorny</i> Cicha et Zapletalova									+									

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**ფორამინიფერების ორი გვარის BULIMINA და BOLIVINA ბანჭოთარების
ისტორია პარატეთისის სარმატულ აუზში**

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რეზიუმე

სარმატული ფორამინიფერები მათი წარმოშობისა და განსხვავებული ცხოვრების ნირის გათვალისწინებით რამოდენიმე ჯგუფად იყოფა (მაისურაძე, 1966, 1971, 1980). საინტერესო ცნობები არსებობს შედარებით სტენოპალური გვარების *Bulimina* და *Bolivina*-ს წარმომადგენლების გავრცელებისა და განვითარების შესახებ პარატეთისის სარმატულ აუზში. აღსანიშნავია, რომ სარმატული ფორამინიფერების კომპლექსებში ისინი მკვეთრად გამოირჩევა ძალიან პატარა (პაწაწინა) ზომებით, აქვთ გავრცელების მცირე არეალი და წარმოდგენილი არიან მხოლოდ რამოდენიმე სახეობით. შეიმჩნევა ნიჟარის აგებულების გამარტივების ტენდენცია დროში.

სარმატული *Bulimina*-ები არიან იმ შუამოცენური ფორამინიფერების შთამომავლები, რომლებიც დიდი გავრცელებით სარგებლობდნენ პარატეთისის ბევრ რეგიონში და იქ მრავალი სახეობით იყვნენ წარმოდგენილი (Livental V.E., 1953; Bogdanovich A.K., 1965; Paghida-Trelea N., 1969; Djanelidze O.I., 1970; Bobrinskaya O.G., Kurenkova V.G., 1986; Gorog, 1992; Krashennnikov V.A. et al., 2003). სარმატულ აუზში კი, მისი გამტკნარების გამო, *Bulimina*-ები აღმოჩნდნენ გაუარესებულ ეკოლოგიურ პირობებში. სარმატული აუზის შედარებით ღრმა ბიოტოპებში ჩამოყალიბდა მათი ღარიბი და დაკნინებული პოპულაციები, რომლებმაც დაიკავეს მეტ-ნაკლებად თავისუფალი და ოპტიმალურ პირობებს მიახლოებული ეკოლოგიური ნიშა. ქვედასარმატულ ნალექებში სახეობების რაოდენობა მეტია –11, შუა სარმატს კი მხოლოდ სამი სახეობა შემორჩა (ტაბ.1). აღსანიშნავია, რომ სარმატული ფორმები წარმოდგენილია მონათესავე სახეობებით, რომლებიც ყველაზე ამტანი აღმოჩნდა და შეეგუა გარემო პირობების გაუარესებას. *Bulimina*-ების განვითარების ისტორია სარმატულ აუზში ამ ფაუნაზე ეკოლოგიური პირობების ზემოქმედების ის მაგალითია, როცა გარემო პირობების გაუარესება დაკნინებისა და გადაგვარების მიზეზი გახდა.

ფაქტიური მასალის ანალიზი გვიჩვენებს, რომ პარატეთისის სარმატულ აუზში გვარი *Bolivina*, მსგავსად *Bulimina*-ებისა, არ სარგებლობს ფართო გავრცელებით და არც სახეობრივი მრავალრიცხოვნება ახასიათებს. სახეობათა დიდი უმრავლესობა ფილოგენეტიკურად დაკავშირებულია შუამოცენურ *Bolivina*-ებთან, რომელთა მრავალრიცხოვანი პოპულაციები არსებობდა პარატეთისის ყველა რეგიონში. შუამოცენურ აუზებში ნორმულმარილიანი ზღვის პირობებთან მიახლოებული გარემო არსებობდა, რაც *Bolivina*-ებისათვის მეტ-ნაკლებად ოპტიმალური იყო და მათ გამრავლებას უწყობდა ხელს. სარმატული დროის განმავლობაში ეკოლოგიური პირობების გაუარესების შემდეგ, რაც ნორმულმარილიან ზღვასთან კავშირის გაწყვეტამ გამოიწვია, *Bolivina*-ები მათი არსებობისათვის უჩვეულო, არახელსაყრელ გარემოში აღმოჩნდა. ამიტომ დიდი ნაწილი, რომელიც ვერ შეეგუა არსებულ მდგომარეობას ამოწვდა. გადარჩენილი ფორმები კი თანდათან დაკნინდა. დროთა განმავლობაში წარმოიქმნა მორფოლოგიურად რამდენადმე შეცვლილი ენდემური სახეობები, რომლებიც შუა სარმატშიც განაგრძობენ არსებობას. მათი რაოდენობა დასავლეთ პარატეთისში მეტია, ვიდრე აღმოსავლეთ პარატეთისში (ტაბ.2).

ფაქტიური მასალა გვიჩვენებს, რომ *Bulimina*-ები და *Bolivina*-ები გვხვდება შედარებით ღრმა უბნებში დალექილ ნალექებში, რომელიც სარმატული აუზის მაქსიმალური დაძირვის ზონებში წარმოიქმნა და ძირითადად თიხებით არის წარმოდგენილი.

ცნობილია, რომ ღრმა უბნებში, ზღვის სანაპირო ან მარჩხ ზოლთან შედარებით, ეკოლოგიური პირობები სტაბილურია და მკვეთრ ცვალებადობას არ განიცდის.

თანამედროვე ნორმულმარილიან ზღვებში, მაგალითად ხმელთაშუა ზღვაში, მარეის (Murray J.W., 1973) მონაცემებით *Bulimina* და *Bolivina* შლამიან გრუნტს ანიჭებს უპირატესობას და არა სანაპირო ზოლს. მათი არსებობისათვის გადამწყვეტია შლამის შემადგენლობა და იმ ქვიშიანი მასალის რაოდენობა, რომელიც შლამშია შერეული. მათთვის ოპტიმალურად მიიჩნევა ისეთი გარემო, სადაც ბიოტოპის ეკოლოგიური პირობები და თანასაზოგადოების შემადგენლობა დიდხანს რჩება სტაბილური. ფორამინიფერები ასეთ გარემოში ნაკლებად ცვალებადია.